

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Soft clays exist at a water content which is close to their liquid limit. Hence, they undergo large amount of settlements even at low values of imposed stresses. Hence, their bearing capacity is very low. Construction of civil engineering infrastructure in such soils is extremely difficult. Therefore, often construction sites in which soft clay strata exist are avoided for construction. But, due to the development of ground improvement techniques, a new phase in geo-technical engineering, weak sites are also improved employing suitable ground improvement techniques. Some of the ground improvement techniques employed in soft clays are chemical stabilization using various additives like lime, CaCl_2 , fly-ash and cement, electro-osmosis, stone columns, grouting and lime-soil columns. Choice of a particular ground improvement technique depends upon factors such as type of soil to be improved, feasibility of technique and degree of ground improvement required.

Reinforced earth has also become a prominent ground improvement technique because of its effectiveness. In this technique different types of inclusions are provided in the soil at various percent contents depending upon the requirement, to improve strength and bearing capacity of the soil. These inclusions can be glass fibers, metal fibers or any bio-degradable fiber also. Further, strip intrusions can also be used made of metals. Reinforced earth has been found to be very successful because of its efficacy in increasing strength and bearing capacity of the soil. The width and the length of these strips, the vertical and horizontal spacing between them and the depth (or thickness) of reinforced earth layer can be designed based on the degree of ground improvement desired.

Geosynthetic reinforcement of ground has been a further development of the concept of reinforced earth, which is recent. Various types of geosynthetics are used as reinforcement members of earth. Geotextiles, geofabrics and geogrids are some of the examples of geosynthetics. Geosynthetic fiber is also used as a recent development of fiber reinforcement of earth. This thesis is a study on improvement on bearing capacity of a soft clay bed over which a

geogrid-reinforced sand cushion is provided. A series of plate load tests was conducted at the laboratory scale to study the improvement in bearing capacity of the system. A high density polyethylene (HDPE) was used as horizontal reinforcement in sand cushion overlying the soft clay bed. Locally available clay was used to form the clay bed of soft consistency. Sand cushion was prepared using different types of sand- fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand. Clay bed was prepared at a constant consistency index of 50% and sand layers were prepared at a constant relative density of 60%. The ratio of sand cushion thickness to clay bed thickness was maintained as 0.25. Circular geogrids of diameter 120mm were used as horizontal reinforcement in the sand cushion. The number of geogrids and spacing between the geogrids were varied. The load-settlement behaviour of the system improved with the introduction of geogrid reinforcement. Load-settlement behaviour further improved with increasing number of geogrid layers and with decreasing spacing between them.

The thesis is organized in 5 chapters including Introduction. Chapter 2 presents a detailed review of literature on soft clays and horizontal geogrid reinforcement used for improving bearing capacity. A detailed experimental investigation is presented in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 discusses the test results. Important conclusions drawn from the experimental studies are presented in Chapter 5.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The safety and economy of any construction depend on the choice of a suitable foundation/substructure. Since this is related to the soil deposit in which the construction is done, the nature of subsoil plays a vital role on the choice of foundation. Soft clays exist all over the world. They are sedimentary soils formed under alluvial, marine, lacustrine or similar environment. Soft clays are highly compressible and possess low shear strength. They give rise to a variety of problems, which include instability and settlement when subjected to loads. Consequently, buildings roads, bridges and under construction in soft clays pose problems in design and construction.

2.2 Origin and Occurrence

Soft clays are fine-grained soils with moderate to high clay fraction and are highly plastic in nature. Soft clays are generally recent sediments laid down by river (alluvium), sea (marine) or lakes (Lacustrine). They exist in three possible river depositional environments, viz., river channel, natural levees, and flood plains. Many of the river deposits are found in the alluvial plains, near the delta, where deposition has occurred during periods of high flooding. These deposits are characterized by bedding and laminations, sometimes interspersed with sand seams. They are however, subjected to repeated desiccation near the ground surface.

Table 2.1 gives the typical index and strength properties of some soft clays. Such clays are found in many areas of Scandinavia, Northern United States, Canada, Mexico, Japan, China, South East Asia, Middle East and India. Most river valleys of the world, such as the Nile in Egypt, Mississippi in USA, Euphrates and Tigris in Iraq, Yangtze in China, Ganga - Brahmaputra in India, Mekong in Indo-China have abundant deposits of soft clay of alluvial origin. Marine clays along the coastal plains of the world also fall under this category.

2.3 Engineering Properties of Soft Clays

The engineering properties of soft clays are characterized by physical properties like grain-size, Atterberg limits, consistency etc. and mechanical properties like shear strength, compressibility, sensitivity and permeability. Understanding of the behavior of soft clay as an engineering material requires evaluation of all the physical and mechanical properties and their inter-relation with each other.

2.3.1 Grain Size

The grain-size distribution is the first step towards identification of the nature of soft clay. High clay fraction renders the soil highly plastic. A vast majority of soft clays contain clay-sized particles varying between 30% and 60% the remaining grain being mainly silt-sized.

2.3.2 Atterberg Limits and Consistency

Clay minerals have sufficient surface forces to attract water molecules. The interactions between clay minerals, water and various chemicals dissolved in water are primarily responsible for the consistency of these soils.

The Atterberg limits along with the natural water content give useful indication of the consistency of a clayey soil. Soft clays have natural water content generally close to the liquid limit. This is typical of all normally consolidated clays, irrespective of their depositional environment. The plastic limit of most inorganic clays varies within a narrow range of 20% - 30% while the liquid limit may vary widely (40% - 100%). Organic clays and clays containing decayed vegetation may, however, show very high liquid limit, sometimes exceeding 200%.

2.3.3 Un-Drained Shear Strength

By far the most important strength parameter influencing stability of soft clays is that corresponding to loading under un-drained condition. As most soft clays exist permanently under the ground water table, they are fully saturated in nature and $q_u = 0$ condition remains valid during construction. Accordingly, the un-drained shear strength of the clay determines the stability in all types of problem viz., bearing capacity, stability of slopes, earth pressure etc.

Because of their high water content, soft clays have un-drained shear strength, c_u less than 25kN/m^2 . In some cases c_u of the order of $10\text{-}15\text{ kN/m}^2$ was also measured. The determination of

in-situ shear strength from laboratory tests is, however, difficult. Effect of stress release, anisotropy, sample size and rate of shear may influence the test results. These clays have high sensitivity and sampling disturbances often cause major reduction in strength. In-situ vane shear test and other penetration tests appear more reliable in such cases.

Soft clays are highly compressible and undergo large deformation even at low superimposed loads. The deformation takes place under un-drained conditions.

Improving the soft clays with various ground improvement techniques is, perhaps, the best alternative. Among the ground improvement techniques in vogue are vertical drains and preloading, vacuum de-watering, stone columns, in-situ deep mixing, thermal treatment, geo-synthetics etc., with these techniques the shear strength and consolidation characteristics are improved and the time for consolidation settlement is reduced. The problem of post consolidation settlement is avoided.

2.4 Soil Improvement With Geo-Synthetics

The technique of soil reinforcement has been extensively used for the last two decades, in a variety of applications ranging from earth retaining structures to sub-grade stabilization. It is one of the most successful and reliable techniques and is fast replacing the other conventional ground improvement methods. The use of geo-synthetics can significantly increase the safety factor, improve performance, and reduce costs over conventional alternative solutions.

Reinforcement strengthens the soil by providing tension and / or lateral confinement. The reinforced ground in combination with reinforcement acts effectively in response to applied load. After the development of the reinforced earth concept (Vidal, 1966) extensive efforts have been made to understand the soil-reinforcement interaction mechanisms. Reinforced soil bed is a soil foundation system containing horizontally embedded geo-synthetics, thin flat metal strips, rods, ties or grids. In case of foundation beds, it is widely accepted that inclusions when oriented in a definite pattern can improve the performance of the foundation soils.

2.5 Studies on The Behaviour of Reinforced Soil Foundations

Over the last few decades, the use of geogrids for soil reinforcement has increased greatly because geogrids are dimensionally stable and having high tensile modulus. Results of several laboratory model tests and a limited number of field tests related to the determination of the

ultimate bearing capacity of surface foundation supported by multi layered geogrid have been reported in literature.

Binquet and Lee (1975 b) gave a theoretical analysis to find out the pressure intensity of isolated strip footings resting on reinforced earth slab for a given settlement (fig. 2.1). A mechanistic working hypothesis regarding significant movement and load transfer has been assumed for the determination of maximum tie force. The footing and zone I of soil, bounded laterally by the loci of maximum shear stresses τ_{xzmax} are assumed to move down, forcing the soil in zone II to move outwards. The reinforcement is assumed to undergo two right angled bends at the failure surface (Fig. 2.2). equilibrium of an element of soil, encompassing a reinforcing strip, in zone I yields the value of tie force which is compared with the tensile strength and the frictional resistance of the strip length in zone II to determine the bearing capacity ratio in rupture and pull-out failures respectively. The exercise is carried out for all the strips and the minimum value of bearing capacity ratio and the corresponding failure mode is determined. Comparison of analytical values with experimental results (Binquet and Lee, 1975 a) showed a fairly good agreement for the case of footing resting on deep homogenous sand.

Singh (1989) and Murthy et al. (1993) modified the analysis proposed by Binquet and Lee (1975) by considering mobilized frictional strength and slip surfaces at the vertical planes passing through the edges of the footing. Kumar (1997) modified the work of Binquet and Lee (1975) logically for analyzing the strip footing resting on reinforced sand. Further, the work was extended to square, rectangular and interfering footings. Al-samadi (1998) extended this analysis to eccentric and inclined loads also. Kumar (2002) extended his earlier work (Kumar, 1997) developing the theoretical analyses for strip and rectangular footings subjected to eccentric-inclined loads.

Ramaswamy and Yong (1983) conducted model tests on strip footings on sand fill, with and without reinforcements. Bearing capacity improved and bearing capacity ratio was found to be in good agreement with the analytical procedures of Binquet and Lee (1975).

Guido et al. (1985) and Guido et al (1986), conducted model plate load tests on uniformly graded sand, un-reinforced and reinforced with layers of different types of geotextiles. The results showed that bearing capacity depended upon the ratio of depth below the footing of the first layer of reinforcement to width of the footing (u/B), ratio of vertical spacing of the layers of reinforcement to width of the footing (z/B), and number of reinforcement layers.

Dembicki et al. (1986) carried-out model plate load tests on granular fill compacted on soft clay with and without geotextile at the interface. Bearing capacity and stiffness of foundation increased with thickness of granular layer and the length of the geotextile.

Tests on strip footings resting on loose sand overlaying weak clay with geotextile placed at sand-clay interface resulted in increased bearing capacity with reduction in the distance of footing from geotextile layer and increase in the embedment depth (Kim and Cho, 1988) as well as the settlement of the footing.

Based on the experimental model tests on geogrid mattresses (yasufuku et al., 1996) bearing capacity improvement were formulated as a function of width of loading normalized by the effective width in the supporting soil layer. Laboratory model studies on a strip footing supported by geocell- reinforcement along with additional planar geogrid reinforced sand resulted in a significant increase in the performance.

Radoslaw and Michalowski (2004) proposed a stability analysis for reinforced foundation soil. A method suggested on limit loads of strip footing over foundation soils reinforced with horizontal layers of geosynthetics. They found that increase in the limit load I_s dependent on the internal friction angle of the soil.

Based on he laboratory experiments conducted by Michalowski et al., (2005) two modes of foundation soil collapse were suggested, one associated with reinforcement slip, and the other due to tensile failure of reinforcement. Limit analysis was applied to both cases, but only the second case yields the strict upper bound value.

Table 2.1 Properties of Soft Clays

clay	Geologic type	Liquid limit (%)	Plastic limit (%)	NMC (%)	Undrained shear strength (KN/m ²)
Mexico city clay	Lacustrine	300	100	300	25
Avonmouth clay	Estuarine	70	20	60	20
England clay	Marine	90	40	60	20
Bombay Marine clay	Marine	40	17	38	12
Norwegian Quick Clay	Alluvial	60	30	50	25
Clay	Marine	80	40	76	20
Normal Calcutta clay	Marine	120	50	80	15
	Marine	60	25	80	10

Fig. 2.1 Three modes of bearing capacity failure in reinforced earth
(After Binquet and Lee, 1975)

Fig. 2.2 Assumed failure mechanism (After Binquet and Lee, 1975)

CHAPTER 3

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

3.1 Introduction

A series of laboratory scale model plate load tests was conducted on a soft clay bed provided with a geogrid-reinforced sand cushion. The load-settlement behaviour of the soft clay bed alone and the clay bed provided with a plain sand cushion (with no geogrid reinforcement) and the clay bed provided with geogrid-reinforced sand cushion was compared.

3.2 Test Materials

3.2.1 Clay

The clay used in the investigation was collected from a depth of 1 m from the ground surface in Vellore, Tamil Nadu state, India. It was light brown in colour. The properties of the clay are shown in the Table 3.1. Based on the plasticity characteristics of the clay, it can be classified as CH according to the USCS classification. The clay was oven dried, powdered and passed through 4.75 mm sieve for use in the experimental investigation.

3.2.2 Sand

Fine sand (0.075 – 0.425 mm), medium sand (0.425 – 2.36 mm) and coarse sand (2.36 – 4.75 mm) were used as sand cushion layers. Figure 3.1 shows the particle size distribution curves of all the three types of sand. Table 3.2 shows the physical index properties of the sand like D_{10} , C_u , C_c and γ_d corresponding to the test relative density of 60%. The sands are all poorly graded (SP) based on their C_u and C_c .

3.2.3 Geogrids

Netlon CE 121 geogrid was used for providing reinforcement in the sand cushion. The properties of the geogrid as supplied by the manufacturers are given in Table 3.3.

3.3 Test Variables

In all the load tests, the clay bed was compacted to a consistency index (I_c) of 50% which was chosen arbitrarily. The thickness of the clay bed was also kept constant in all the tests as 200 mm. All the clay beds were compacted to a dry density of 13kN/m^3 .

All the sand cushion layers were compacted in a dry state, at an arbitrary constant relative density (D_r) of 60%. The γ_d of all the sands corresponding to the relative density of 60% was determined based on pilot tests. The thickness of the sand cushion was kept constant at 50 mm. The diameter of the bearing plate was 60 mm. The diameter of the test geogrid was fixed at 120 mm. The number of geogrids (n) was varied as 1, 2 and 3. The spacing between the geogrids (s) was kept constant at 10 mm. The depth of the top geogrid from the bottom of the bearing plate (u) was also kept constant at 10 mm. Plate load tests were conducted in cylindrical test moulds of diameter 300 mm and height 300 mm.

3.4 Compaction of Clay Bed and Sand Cushion

As already mentioned, the clay beds were compacted to a dry unit weight of 13kN/m^3 . Oven dried and powdered clay was passed through 4.75 mm and was used in the preparation of test clay beds. The oven dry clay was cooled to the room temperature and mixed thoroughly with required amount of water which was 2.5%, to give the predetermined consistency index of 50%. The clay bed was compacted in 4 layers of equal thickness 50mm. To insure a uniform dry unit weight in all the clay layers, the thickness of clay layers was carefully checked. When the compaction of the clay bed was over, sand cushion of 50 mm thickness was compacted over the clay bed so that its relative density was equal to 60%. In the case of geogrid reinforced sand beds, geogrids were placed at the required depths and spacing during the process of compaction of sand layers.

3.5 Test Procedure

After compaction was over, the bearing plate (60 mm) was kept on the sand bed or the clay bed as the case may be so that its centre of gravity coincides with that of the test tank. Static loads each of weight 28.4N were applied on the test plate. Under each increment of load, deformation was noted with the help two dial gauges, the average of which was reported as the deformation.

Each increment of load was applied for a duration of 12 hours, within which the deformation was observed to have ceased. Load-settlement behaviour was studied through plots between the applied load (N) and deformation.

Table 3.1 Index Properties of Test Clay

Specific gravity	2.68
Liquid limit (%)	60
Plastic limit (%)	26
Plasticity index (%)	34
<i>Compaction properties</i>	
OMC (%)	21
MDD (kN/m ³)	16.6
USCS classification	CH

Table 3.2. Properties of Test Sands

Property	Fine sand	Medium sand	Coarse sand
Dry unit weight (for $D_r = 60\%$), kN/m ³	16.19	15.77	15.43
D_{10} (mm)	0.25	0.59	1.3
D_{max} (mm)	0.425	2.36	4.75
C_u	1.4	1.995	2.07
C_c	1.17	1.12	1.25
Classification (USCS)	Poorly graded	Poorly graded	Poorly graded
Classification symbol	SP	SP	SP

Table 3.3 Properties of Geogrid

SPECIFICATION	RANGE
Mesh aperture size	6 x 6 mm
Mesh thickness	3.3 mm
Structural weight ($\pm 5\%$)	7.30 g/m ²
Colour	Black
Polymer	HDPE
Tensile Strength	7.68 kN/m ²
Elongation at max. load.	20.2%

Fig 3.1 Grain size distribution curves for all types of sands

Fig 3.2 Line Sketch

Fig 3.3 Experimental Setup

Fig 3.4 Geogrid Reinforcement

CHAPTER 4

DISCUSSION OF TEST RESULTS

4.1 Introduction

The results of plate load tests conducted on the clay bed alone, clay bed with plain (or unreinforced) cushion made of fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand and clay bed with geogrid reinforced cushion made of fine sand medium sand and coarse sand are presented and discussed in the following sections.

4.2 Effect of Sand Cushion on Load-Settlement Characteristics of Clay Bed

Fig 4.1 shows the load-settlement characteristics of clay bed alone, and clay bed provided with cushion made of fine sand, medium sand, and coarse sand. The load-settlement characteristics are shown in the form of graphical plots between loads (N) and settlement (mm). Clay bed alone (without any cushion) underwent a settlement of 32mm under an applied load of 140N. When clay bed was provided with sand cushion, the total settlement decreased in comparison to that in the case of clay bed alone for a given load, indicating improvement in load-settlement behaviour. Among the cushion sands used, fine sand resulted in the best load settlement response. The next best load-settlement response was obtained in the case of clay bed provided with cushion with coarse sand. The least load-settlement response was obtained in the case of clay bed provided with medium sand. Fine sand resulted in the highest dry density for the test relative density of 60% (see Table 4.2). The load response decreased in the case of coarse sand and medium sand because the dry density decreased to medium sand and to coarse sand. Coarse sand gave a better load response than medium sand because of its higher angle of internal friction and interlocking. For example, the load required to be applied on clay bed alone for a deformation of 5 mm was 36N. But, when the clay bed was provided with cushions of fine sand, coarse sand and medium sand the loads required to be applied on fine sand , coarse sand and medium sand for the same deformation of 5mm were respectively 70N, 50N and 44N. This meant that the load required to be applied for $\delta=5\text{mm}$ showed an improvement of 94%, 39% and 22% respectively in case of fine sand, coarse sand and medium sand over clay bed alone.

4.3 Effect of Geogrid Reinforcement on Load-Settlement Behaviour

Figures 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4 show the load-settlement characteristics of clay bed alone, clay bed provided with plain (or un-reinforced) sand cushion and clay bed provided with geogrid reinforced sand cushion. The data shown in the Figures 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4 are respectively for fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand. The load-settlement behaviour improved when the clay bed was provided with sand cushion. The load-settlement behaviour further improved when the sand cushions were reinforced with horizontal geogrid layers. Horizontal geogrid reinforcement placed beneath the footing intercepts the failure zone in sands. Further the stress distribution area increases at a given depth in the sand bed because of a wider distribution of stress affected by horizontal geogrid reinforcement. Hence, the stress at a given horizontal plane in the sand bed reduces resulting in a smaller amount of settlement. Under the applied compressive load, geogrid bends at the edges of the footing because the diameter of the geogrid is greater than the dia of the footing, and also because the geogrid intercepts the failure plane. Bending of the geogrids generates tensile forces in the geogrids. Geogrids resist these tensile stresses resulting in improved load-settlement behaviour of the system. Hence, the load-settlement curves of clay-bed with geogrid-reinforced sand cushion lay above those for plain or un-reinforced sand cushion and clay bed alone. Further, it was observed that the load-settlement behaviour further improved when the number of geogrids was increased. When the number of geogrids was increased confinement of sand layer increased resulting in a better load response. Hence the load-settlement curves for sand cushion with higher number of geogrids lay above those for sand cushion with lower number of geogrids. This phenomenon was observed in all types of sand used for forming the sand cushion.

From Figures 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4 the applied vertical compressive load for a deformation of 5 mm was 37 N. However, when the clay bed was provided with sand cushion, the vertical load required to be applied for the same deformation of 5mm was respectively 70N, 45N and 50N for fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand. When geogrid reinforcement was provided, the vertical load required to be applied for the same deformation of 5 mm increased. When the number of geogrids in the sand layers increased, the vertical load required for the same deformation further increased. The phenomenon was observed in all types of sand (see Figures 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4).

When $n=1$ the vertical compressive load required to be applied for a deformation of 5 mm was respectively 84N, 74N and 127N. When the number of geogrids was increased as $n=2$ and 3, the vertical load further increased to 125 N and 169 N in fine sand, 92N and 120 in medium sand and 155N and 172N in coarse sand. The entire test data are tabulated in Table 4.3. It may be mentioned here that the vertical distance between the base plate of the footing and the top geogrid (u) and the spacing between the geogrid were kept constant at 10 mm in the work. The significant improvement in load-settlement behaviour observed when the number of geogrids was increased can be attributed to higher confinement effect in the reinforced layer and higher interlocking effect between the geogrids and the sand medium (irrespective of the type of sand used in the sand cushion). The percentage improvement in the load to be applied for a deformation of 5mm when 'n' was increased to 3 was 357%, 365% and 224% in the case of fine sand, coarse sand and medium sand with reference to clay bed alone. With reference to plain (or un-reinforced sand layer), percentage improvement was 141%, 244% and 167% in the case of fine sand, coarse sand and medium sand respectively.

Figure 4.5 shows load-settlement behaviour of clay bed alone and geogrid-reinforced fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand for ($n=3$). The load-settlement curves of fine sand and coarse sand were close to each other. However, at higher loads beyond 200N coarse sand gave a better behaviour. This means that, for $n=3$, coarse sand resulted in the best load-settlement behaviour. This can be attributed to the higher angle of internal friction (ϕ) of coarse sand and the higher interlocking effect obtained in coarse sand at higher number of geogrids.

Figure 6 shows the effect of D_{10} of all test sands on the compressive load (N) required for causing a settlement of 5mm. The data pertain to various values of n . The compressive load (N) increased with increasing n for all D_{10} . The compressive load increased with increasing particle size of the sand layer. Hence, the compressive load was the highest for coarse sand. The next highest compressive load was observed in fine sand because fine sands resulted in maximum dry unit weight. The compressive load corresponding to medium sand was lowest.

Figure 7 shows the variation of compressive load required for $\delta = 5\text{mm}$ with number of geogrid layers (n) for fine sand, medium sand and coarse sand. For all values of n , coarse sand resulted in the highest compressive load and medium sand resulted in the lowest compressive load. When $n = 0$ fine sand resulted in the highest vertical compressive load because of its high dry unit

weight. However, with the introduction of geogrid reinforcement interlocking effect was greater in coarse sand resulting in higher vertical loads required for $\delta = 5\text{mm}$.

Figure 8 shows the effect of non dimensional $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$ with vertical compressive load required for a settlement of 5 mm. The data shown indicate the interlocking effect on compressive load in various types of sand. The data indicate that coarse sand, having a low ratio of $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$, resisted the compressive load most effectively because of its high angle of internal friction and interlocking. This was true for all values of n. The case of $n = 3$ resulted in the best load response.

The efficacy of sand cushion or geogrid reinforcement of sand cushion in increasing the load-settlement response is expressed as a non-dimensional quantity called load improvement ratio (LIR) which is defined below:

$$\text{LIR (clay)} = \frac{\text{(Load for a given settlement in (sand cushion or reinforced sand cushion))}}{\text{(Load for a given settlement in clay bed)}} \quad \text{----- (4.1)}$$

As it has been calculated with reference to clay bed alone, it is indicated as LIR (clay).

Figure 9 shows the variation of LIR with D_{10} for various values of n. LIR increased with D_{10} for all values of n beyond $n=0$. This indicates that coarse sand with its high angle of internal friction resulted in maximum load-settlement improvement in geogrid-reinforced cases.

Figure 10 shows the influence of number of geogrids (n) on LIR. LIR increased with number of geogrids (n) for all the test sands. But the load-settlement improvement was significant in the case of coarse sand followed by fine sand and medium sand.

Figure 11 shows the variation of LIR with non-dimensional ratio $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$ for all values of n. LIR increased with increasing $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$ from medium sand to fine sand, reflecting the improved load-settlement response in fine sand compared to medium sand. LIR was the highest in coarse sand reflecting the best interlocking effect obtained in geogrid reinforced coarse sand.

LIR was calculated for various cases of geogrid reinforced sand layer with reference to unreinforced sand layer (see Table 4.3). This is indicated as LIR (sand cushion). LIR (sand cushion) is defined as:

$$\text{LIR (sand cushion)} = \frac{\text{(Load for a given settlement in geogrid-reinforced sand cushion)}}{\text{(Load for the same settlement in the case of plain or un-reinforced sand layer)}} \quad \text{----- (4.2)}$$

Fig 4.12 shows the variation of LIR (sand cushion) with D_{10} for various values of n . LIR increases with D_{10} for all values of n . This was because the load-settlement response improved with increasing particle size of the sand cushion layer. For all values of D_{10} , LIR increased with increasing number of geogrid layers (n). As the number of geogrid layers (n) increased, the compressive load response of the geogrid-reinforced sand layer improved.

Fig 4.13 shows the variation of LIR (sand cushion) with number of geogrid layers (n). The data pertain to various sand beds. LIR increased with increasing n for all types of sand used in the sand cushion. The load-settlement response improved as the particle size of the sand cushion increased, for all values of n . Thus, LIR increased from fine to medium to coarse sand for all n .

Fig 4.14 shows the variation of LIR (sand cushion) with $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$ for all values of n . D_{aperture} of the geogrid was fixed as 6mm. Hence, as D_{max} of the sand used in the sand cushion increased, the ratio $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$ decreased. The ratio $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$ indicates the optimum interlocking effect of geogrid-sand cushion system. LIR decreased with increasing $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$ for all values of n , indicating that the load response was the best in the case of coarse sand. As already observed, LIR increased with increasing n irrespective of the type of sand cushion or $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$.

Table 4.1. Vertical compressive loads (N) for different cases ($\delta = 5$ mm)

Test case	Vertical load (N)	% Improvement with reference to clay bed alone	% Improvement with reference to un- reinforced sand cushion
Clay bed	37	-	-
Fine sand	70	89	-
Un-reinforced			
Reinforced (n=1)	84	127	20
(n=2)	125	278	79
(n=3)	169	357	141
Medium sand	45	22	-
Un-reinforced			
Reinforced (n=1)	74	100	64
(n=2)	92	149	104
(n=3)	120	224	167
Coarse sand	50	35	-
Un-reinforced			
Reinforced (n=1)	127	243	154
(n=2)	155	319	210
(n=3)	172	365	244

Fig 4.1. Load-settlement characteristics ($n = 0$)

Fig 4.2. Load-settlement characteristics; fine sand ($n = 0, 1, 2$ and 3) and clay bed

Fig 4.3. Load-settlement characteristics; medium sand ($n = 0, 1, 2$ and 3) and clay bed

Fig 4.4. Load-settlement characteristics; coarse sand ($n = 0, 1, 2$ and 3) and clay bed

Fig 4.5. Load-settlement characteristics of clay and sand layers (n = 3)

Fig 4.6. Effect of D_{10} on load for a settlement of 5 mm; n = 0, 1, 2 and 3

Fig 4.7. Variation of load for 5 mm settlement with n

Fig 4.8. Variation of load for 5 mm settlement with $D_{aperture}/D_{max}$

Fig 4.9. Variation of LIR with D_{10}

Fig 4.10. Variation of LIR with number of geogrids (n)

Fig 4.11. Variation of LIR with $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$

Fig.4.12. Variation of LIR (as compared with unreinforced case) with D_{10}

Fig.4.13. Variation of LIR (as compared with unreinforced case) with number of geogrids (n)

Fig.4.14. Variation of LIR (as compared with unreinforced case) with $D_{aperture}/D_{max}$

CONCLUSION

- The load-settlement behaviour improved when the clay bed was provided with sand cushion. The load-settlement behaviour further improved when the sand cushion was reinforced with horizontal geogrid layers.
- Further, it was observed that the load-settlement behaviour further improved when the number of geogrids was increased. When the number of geogrids was increased confinement of sand layer increased resulting in a better load response. Hence, the load-settlement curves for sand cushion with higher number of geogrids lay above those for sand cushion with lower number of geogrids. This phenomenon was observed in all types of sand used for forming the sand cushion.
- The percentage improvement in the load to be applied for a deformation of 5mm when n was increased to 3 was 357%, 365% and 224% in the case of fine sand, coarse sand and medium sand with reference to clay bed alone
- With reference to plain (or un-reinforced sand layer), percentage improvement was 141%, 244% and 167% in the case of fine sand, coarse sand and medium sand respectively.
- For $n = 3$, coarse sand resulted in the best load-settlement behaviour. This can be attributed to the higher angle of internal friction (ϕ) of coarse sand and the higher interlocking effect obtained in coarse sand at higher number of geogrids.
- The compressive load (N) increased with increasing n for all D_{10} . The compressive load increased with increasing particle size of the sand layer. Hence, the compressive load was the highest for coarse sand. The next highest compressive load was observed in fine sand because fine sands resulted in maximum dry unit weight. The compressive load corresponding to medium sand was lowest.
- For all values of n , coarse sand resulted in the highest vertical compressive load (required for settlement of $\delta = 5\text{mm}$) and medium sand resulted in the lowest compressive load. When $n = 0$ fine sand resulted in the highest vertical compressive load because of its high dry unit weight.
- The data indicate that coarse sand, having a low ratio of $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$, resisted the compressive load most effectively because of its high angle of internal friction and interlocking. This was true for all values of n . The case of $n = 3$ resulted in the best load response.
- LIR increased with D_{10} for all values of n beyond $n=0$. LIR increased with number of geogrids (n) for all the test sands. But the load-settlement improvement was significant in the case of coarse sand followed by fine sand and medium sand
- LIR increased with increasing $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$ from medium sand to fine sand, reflecting the improved load-settlement response in fine sand compared to medium sand. LIR was the

highest in coarse sand reflecting the best interlocking effect obtained in geogrid reinforced coarse sand.

- LIR (sand cushion) increased with D_{10} for all values of n . This was because the load-settlement response improved with increasing particle size of the sand cushion layer. For all values of D_{10} , LIR increased with increasing number of geogrid layers (n). As the number of geogrid layers (n) increased, the compressive load response of the geogrid-reinforced sand layer improved.
- LIR (sand cushion) decreased with increasing $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$ for all values of n , indicating that the load response was the best in the case of coarse sand. As already observed, LIR increased with increasing n irrespective of the type of sand cushion or $D_{\text{aperture}}/D_{\text{max}}$.

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